

Examination Malpractice: The Bane Of Achievement Of Quality In Educational Assessment In Owerri Education Zone 1 Of Imo State

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ABSTRACT

Examination malpractice is a plague that has critically ruined the credibility of our examination system, compromised the quality of our certificates and indeed our education system. The study investigated the public secondary school teachers' views on the effects of examination malpractice in the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State. The study employed a survey research design. The population of the study comprised public secondary school teachers in the Zone totaling 2, 644. The sample size for the study was 661 (201 male and 460 female) teachers representing 25% of the population. The sample was obtained using convenience sampling method, evenly distributed across the Zone. The study was guided by one research question and one hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument for data collection was the researchers' structured questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.89 (Cronbach Alpha). The findings indicated that both male and female secondary school teachers independently opined that examination malpractice poses a great danger to the validity and reliability of the education system, which negatively affects both moral and intellectual development of the students. It was recommended that the society should promote hard work, honesty and integrity, and punish perpetrators of bribery and examination malpractice.

Keywords: Examination Malpractice, Achievement, Quality, Credibility.

INTRODUCTION

Examinations have been globally acknowledged as the choicest means of assessment. They are meant to measure the academic attainment of students and to determine whether they have reached a standard of academic learning and knowledge. According to Oduwaiye in Jibrin and Ibrahim (2023), examination is an organized assessment technique which presents individuals with a series of questions or tasks geared towards ascertaining the individual acquired knowledge and skills. Examinations are instruments by which students' instructional achievement outcomes can be measured. Examinations are considered the basis for promotion to higher classes, a source of motivation for learners to advance to additional studies, and a basis for prediction about students' future education and job aptitudes (Makaula, 2018). Teachers and counsellors rely on them for a comprehensive evaluation of their students and clients.

Usually, the rudimentary functions of examinations are to generate data for promotion, certification, selection, prediction, monitoring, research and instructional/motivational aids. As a result of above, there are customary rules, principles, code of conduct or ethics expected to guide every examination. The defilement of these set rules is known as examination malpractice.

Examination malpractice is an act that disrespects all rules and regulations guiding the good conduct of any examination or any evaluation process (Dajwan *et al.*, 2021). It is an illegal act by the examinee or examiner or his agent before, during or after the examination with the intent to make the examinee have an undue advantage or earn an unmerited grade (Asuru in Asuru & Njigwum, 2021). Bruno and Obidigbo (2012) viewed examination malpractice as any action carried out by stakeholders such as educational administrators, teachers, parents or students that is likely to render the assessment or examination ineffective or useless. In their own opinion, Odongba (2012) maintained that examination malpractice is an act of wrong doing carried out by candidates or groups of candidates or any other person with the intention to cheat and gain undue advantages in an examination. Awanbor (2014) opined that examination malpractice is the application of unusual means to obtain a score or set of scores that is normally beyond the mental capability or the state of preparedness of a candidate for the examination. The rampant occurrence of examination malpractice in the recent times has become an issue of growing importance and concern in the Nigeria education system.

This evil has eaten deep into the fabrics of the Nigerian educational system and has constituted a major threat to the credibility of educational assessment in Nigeria. It is disheartening to know that some parents, teachers, examination bodies, Government and society members were found to have been involved in examination malpractices (Ojetunde, 2023). It becomes a waste of time and resources on the part of the examining body and the society at large because the reliability of scores of most students are in doubt (Dajwan *et al.*, 2021). This is because if there is no value in the attainment of education, the certificate obtained has no value (Ojetunde, 2023). The concept of quality assessment in education has been the central theme for education in many countries of the world, Nigeria inclusive.

There are several forms of examination malpractice. According to Onyibe, Uma and Ibina (2015), examination malpractice ranges from impersonation, leakage of questions, tampering with results, computer fraud to fraudulent practices by invigilators. Forms of examination malpractice perpetuated by stakeholders are copying from colleagues, seeking and giving assistance from invigilators, teachers, smuggling copied answers to students in the examinations; parents and school authorities aiding leakage of examination questions, security personnel aiding and abetting illegalities, and referring to books kept at places of convenience (Gyamfi, 2022). Ajere (2013) outlined the following forms of examination malpractice:

- *Falsification of examination result either by examinees or even examiners.*
- *Storage of questions and answers inside mobile phones.*
- *Creation of examination centers outside the coverage of internet detections.*
- *Accessing examination questions through the internet on the eve of the examination for discussion over-night.*
- *Conniving with examination body unfaithful staff to access live questions through the internet.*
- *Giving or receiving assistance of varied kinds from parents and other allied groups.*
- *Causing confusion and distraction to enable prepared answers come into the examination hall.*
- *Teachers or lecturers soliciting and wooing colleagues for the award of unmerited grades to their favourite student or students or even parents acting at the same capacity.*
- *Examinee having foreknowledge of the questions before the actual examination time (leakage).*
- *Verbal exchange of ideas and giraffing due to proximity of test-mates and over crowdedness.*
- *Bribing invigilators and supervisors so as to turn 'blind eyes' to malpractice or giving examination contractors and impersonators the questions to take away so as to prepare answers outside the examination hall.*
- *Awarding inflated marks to students by teachers.*

- *Examinees issuing threat to examiners.*

Education is an instrument for national development. Thus, Nigeria being a developing country depends on her education for the development of high-level manpower to maintain the various sectors of the nation's economy (Ojetunde, 2023). Akaranga and Ongong (2013) asserted that examination malpractice poses a great threat to the validity and reliability of the education system. They described it as a trend that is harmful not only to moral development but also to the intellectual development of the students. If the trend is not controlled, not only will the programmes' graduates lack the moral discipline but they will also lack the knowledge, skills and competence necessary to exploit the resources at their disposal.

Examination malpractice is a vice that has bedeviled the Nigerian educational system for many years. Giving credence to the above, Okoh (2014) argued that examination malpractice is an unacceptable behaviour that is continually destroying the Nigerian educational system. Even with the promulgation of Decree No 33 of 1999 (Now Act of parliament) designed to check examination malpractice; the crime appears to be on the increase (Dajwan *et al.*, 2021). As evidence of high incidence of examination malpractice during public examinations in Nigeria, Adebumiti in Okoye (2024) presented statistics which showed that in 2018, out of 1, 572, 396 candidates that sat for the West African Senior School Certificate Examination, 102, 058 had their results withheld over examination malpractice; in 2019, the results of 180, 205 out of 1, 590, 173 candidates were seized, while in 2020 those of 215, 149 were withheld out of 1, 538, 445 candidates.

As a result, examination malpractice has placed question mark on the quality of the Nigerian educational system and thus its certification recognition. This report implies that a large percentage of the students engage in examination malpractice. While most of the concern is focused on the causes, little attention has been given to the its threat to achievement of quality in educational assessment. However, some researchers have pointed some possible dangers of examination malpractice on the integrity of our educational system. For example, Onyibe *et al* (2015) opined that the implication of examination malpractice is that documents or certificates emanating from such country will be treated with suspicion as is the case of Nigeria today. Examination malpractice frustrates the use of examination for educational reforms, as it will be difficult for the administrators of education to know the extent to which the objectives of education are being served (Usman & Aliyu, 2023). The products of such a system can only grow up to be cynics, narrow minded, myopic, unintelligent, deceptive, closed minded, one-sided beings who would be indifferent to the issues of life and powerless to act, create or succeed (Oyinye & Alaweze cited in Money & Money, 2013). According to Okanezi and Eguzozie (2018), many good students have been denied admission by corrupt ones who through examination malpractice have better scores and grades. Okoh (2014), was of the opinion that that consequences of examination malpractice in Nigeria included lack of recognition of academic qualification, frequent cancellations, suspension of results, unproductive labour force, lack of confidence in the educational system, molestation and harassment of students by lecturers, and vice versa. Asuru and Njigwum (2021) observed that examination malpractice has elevated mediocrity to an art and thus sacrificing excellence on the altar of mediocrity. Chaminuka and Ndudzo (2014) noted that these acts have very serious economic, political, and social consequences that can cripple a nation. This was supported by the submission of Asuru and Njigwum (2021) that our society is currently bedeviled with an ever-increasing spate of perversion of justice, political thuggery, cultism, bribery and corruption, corner-cutting, electoral fraud, and the like. This is mainly because we have cultivated the attitude of reaping where we did not sow.

The current study addressed the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Nigeria using Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State as a point of contact. Academic attainments, achievements or qualifications should be based on the true abilities, knowledge and skills of the candidate rather than engaging in examination cheating and result manipulation. It is hoped that the findings of this study would generate information which education policy makers, including the personnel working at the examining bodies, would use to compare with and add to the already existing body of knowledge on examination malpractice.

Purpose of the Study

This study aimed at investigating the effects of examination malpractice in the achievement of quality in educational assessment.

Research Questions

The following research question was raised to guide the study.

- i. Does examination malpractice affect the achievement of quality in educational assessment?

Hypotheses

In line with the objective of this study, the following hypothesis was postulated:

- i. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design: Survey research design was adopted for the study. The appropriateness of the design stemmed from the postulation of Nworgu (2015), that survey research design is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be a representative of the entire group. This design was considered appropriate because only a part of the population was studied and findings were used to generalize for the entire population.

Participants: The area of this study was Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State, with 79 public secondary schools. The population of the study consisted of 2, 644 (501 male and 2, 143 female) secondary school teachers in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State (SEMB, 2024). The sample size for the study was 661 teachers representing 25% of the population. The sample was obtained using convenience sampling method, evenly distributed across the five Local Government Areas of the Zone.

Instrument: The instrument for data collection was the researchers' developed structured questionnaire of the 4 – point scale Likert format of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point, titled: Effects of Examination Malpractice on the Achievement of Quality in Educational Assessment (EEMAQEA). EEMAQEA had two sections. Section A was designed to sought information on demographic variables from the teachers while Section B contained 20 items constructed to generate information on the “effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment.” The initial draft of the instrument, objective, research question and hypothesis were validated by two Lecturers in Measurement and Evaluation and one Lecturer from Educational Administration, all from Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri. Their suggestions and corrections were effected in the final copy of the instrument. The reliability index was obtained using Cronbach Alpha. The instrument was administered once to 15 public secondary school teachers who were not involved in the study. The coefficient of reliability obtained was 0.89.

Tools of Data Analysis: The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics (mean) while the hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics (t-test) at 5% level of significance.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

The collected data were analyzed and the results were presented in Tables 1 and 2, based on the stated research question and hypothesis.

Research question: *Does examination malpractice negativity affects the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State?*

Table 1: Public Secondary School Teachers responses on the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1	Examination malpractice makes education statuses compromised	260	220	122	59	3.03	Agreed
2	Examination malpractice decreases the nation’s educational integrity	251	231	116	63	3.01	Agreed
3	Examination malpractice poses a great threat to the validity and reliability of the educational system	272	242	103	44	3.12	Agreed
4	Examination malpractice makes students loss self confidence	301	225	94	41	3.18	Agreed
5	Examination malpractice helps in the production of certificated illiterates	288	205	107	61	3.08	Agreed
6	Examination malpractice causes national underdevelopment	337	250	40	34	3.34	Agreed
7	Examination malpractice leads to production of quacks as professionals	218	221	145	77	2.87	Agreed
8	Examination malpractice makes wrong people advance to higher educational institutions	269	219	109	64	3.04	Agreed
9	Examination malpractice leads to irreversible loss of international credibility	277	233	102	49	3.11	Agreed
10	Examination malpractice promotes academic laziness	253	229	110	69	3.00	Agreed
11	Examination malpractice leads to brain drain	239	237	106	79	2.96	Agreed
12	Examination malpractice is one of the negative factors affecting educational objectives	253	229	118	61	3.01	Agreed
13	Examination malpractice frustrates the use of examination for educational reforms.	262	222	113	64	3.03	Agreed
14	Examination malpractice helps in the overall reduction in quality of education	271	215	104	71	3.03	Agreed
15	Examination malpractice has elevated mediocrity	280	204	115	62	3.06	Agreed
16	Examinations malpractice produce candidates with low moral and academic values.	237	200	140	84	2.89	Agreed
17	Examination malpractice ruins the sustainable development goals	228	221	125	87	2.89	Agreed
18	With examination malpractice, the credibility of school assessment process is lost.	279	220	108	54	3.09	Agreed
19	Examination malpractice causes lack of recognition of academic qualifications acquired in Nigeria	267	230	105	59	3.06	Agreed
20	Examination malpractice causes frequent cancellation and suspension of results and the suffering of innocent candidates	243	227	112	79	2.95	Agreed
Total						3.04	

Table 1 shows that all the items had mean score greater than 2.50 which is the mean value of the four-point scale. It implies that the teachers opined that these items were true for the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State.

Table 4: Analysis of the Mean Ratings of Male and Female Teachers' Responses on the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State According to Gender.

Variables	Males Mean Score (SD)	Females Mean Score (SD)	Mean Score Difference (95% CI)	t-Statistic	p-value
Gender	3.101 (0.196)	3.0400 (0.0789)	0.0610 (-0.0863, 0.2083)	0.91	0.382

As observed in Table 2, there was no significant difference between male and female teachers' mean responses on the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State, since the *p*-value (0.382) is greater than the level of significance (0.05). Thus, the observed differences in the teachers' perceived responses were not significant.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study investigated the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment in Owerri Education Zone 1 of Imo State. The findings of this study revealed that the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment was generally high based on items measured (having grand mean of **3.04**). These results aligned with the submission of Adebumiti in Okoye (2024) which portrayed evidence of high incidence of examination malpractice during public examinations in Nigeria. Even with the promulgation of Decree No 33 of 1999 (Now Act of Parliament) designed to check examination malpractice; the crime appears to be on the increase (Dajwan *et al.*, 2021). Also, based on the positive views of the teachers, the outcome of the study also agreed with Okoh (2014) who argued that examination malpractice is an unacceptable behaviour that is continually destroying the Nigerian educational system. The study also revealed that examination malpractice decreases the nation's educational integrity, which is in agreement with the declaration of Onyibe *et al* (2015) that the implication of examination malpractice is that documents or certificates emanating from such country will be treated with suspicion as is the case of Nigeria today. Again, one of the findings showed that examination malpractice helps in the production of certificated illiterates. This finding confirmed the submission of Oyinye and Alaweze cited in Money and Money (2013), that the products of such a system can only grow up to be cynics, narrow minded, myopic, unintelligent, deceptive, closed minded, one-sided beings who would be indifferent to the issues of life and powerless to act, create or succeed. National under development and production of quacks as professionals were found to be caused by examination malpractice. The findings above agreed with the assertion of Chaminuka and Ndudzo (2014) that examination malpractice has very serious economic, political, and social consequences that can cripple a nation. This was supported by the submission of Asuru and Njigwum (2021) that our society is currently bedeviled with an ever-increasing spate of perversion of justice, political thuggery, cultism, bribery and corruption, corner-cutting, electoral fraud, and the like. Irreversible loss of international credibility, promotion of academic laziness and brain drain were revealed to be negative impacts of examination malpractice affecting educational objectives. These were in agreement with findings of Akaranga and Ongong (2013) that examination malpractice is a trend that is harmful not only to moral development but also to the intellectual development of the students. If the trend is not controlled, not only will the programmes' graduates lack the moral discipline but they will also lack the knowledge, skills and competence necessary to exploit the resources at their disposal. Negative affect on educational objectives, frustrating the use of examination for educational reforms, loss in the credibility of school assessment process and helping in the overall reduction in quality of education, were found to be problems created by examination malpractice. The findings aligned with the opinion of

Usman and Aliyu (2023) that examination malpractice frustrates the use of examination for educational reforms, as it will be difficult for the administrators of education to know the extent to which the objectives of education are being served. Akaranga and Ongong (2013) asserted that examination malpractice poses a great threat to the validity and reliability of the education system. Deacceleration of the sustainable development goals was revealed to be part of the problems created by examination malpractice. Education is an instrument for national development. Thus, Nigeria being a developing country depends on her education for the development of high-level manpower to maintain the various sectors of the nation's economy (Ojetunde, 2023). Examination malpractice causes frequent cancellation and suspension of results and the suffering of innocent candidates. These findings aligned with the opinion of Okoh (2014). They observed that consequences of examination malpractice in Nigeria included lack of recognition of academic qualification, frequent cancellations, suspension of results, unproductive labour force, lack of confidence in the educational system, molestation and harassment of students by lecturers, and vice versa.

In the test of hypotheses, it was revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the negative effects of examination malpractice on the achievement of quality in educational assessment based on gender. Thus, the observed differences in the teachers' perceived responses were not significant.

CONCLUSION

The feat of an educational system depends totally upon the effectiveness of its examination system, as it is an essential constituent of teaching and learning process. Examination malpractice is known to be an evil act and as such, unacceptable everywhere in the world. It is a vice that has bedeviled the Nigerian educational system. Engaging in it poses a great danger to the validity and reliability of the education system, which negatively affects both moral and intellectual development of the students. This will in turn decrease the nation's educational integrity and lack of recognition of academic qualifications acquired in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The society should promote hard work, honesty and integrity, and punish perpetrators of bribery and examination malpractice
- ii. There should be motivation for teachers and examination officials so that they cannot be prone to temptation
- iii. Disciplinary measures should be taken on perpetrators of examination malpractice without fear or favour.
- iv. Reorientation of students can contribute in no small measure to changing their mind set about examination malpractices.
- v. During examination period, movement of unauthorized persons in and around the venues should be prevented.

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